

Raw read metadata

Dataset title

Seven years in formalin: metabarcoding mesozooplankton preserved in buffered formalin from the Northern Adriatic Sea

Dataset description

This dataset contains raw metabarcoding sequencing reads generated from mesozooplankton samples collected in the Northern Adriatic Sea and preserved in buffered formalin for approximately seven years before molecular processing.

The samples were collected at the MAMBO-1 meteo-oceanographic buoy in the Gulf of Trieste, Northern Adriatic Sea. DNA was extracted from formalin-preserved mesozooplankton material and used for metabarcoding analyses targeting multiple molecular markers.

The dataset supports reproducibility of the associated study on the feasibility, limitations, and taxonomic recovery of metabarcoding from long-term formalin-preserved mesozooplankton samples.

Sampling information

- Sampling area: Gulf of Trieste, Northern Adriatic Sea
- Sampling site: MAMBO-1 buoy
- Coordinates: 45°41'51.7" N, 13°42'29.9" E
- Sampling year: 2017
- Sample type: mesozooplankton community samples
- Sampling method: vertical haul using a WP2 plankton net
- Mesh size: 200 µm
- Preservation: 4% buffered formalin
- Preservation time before molecular analysis: approximately seven years

Sequencing data

The uploaded files include demultiplexed raw sequencing reads in compressed FASTQ format.

Expected file format:

MAMBO1_YYYY-MM_marker_R1.fastq.gz
MAMBO1_YYYY-MM_marker_R2.fastq.gz

where:

- `MAMBO1` identifies the sampling site
- `YYYY-MM` identifies the sampling year and month
- `marker` identifies the amplified metabarcoding marker, i.e. `COI`, `18SV4`, or `18SV9`
- `R1` and `R2` indicate forward and reverse reads

Molecular markers

The dataset includes raw reads generated for the following metabarcoding markers:

- COI: `mICOLintF` - `jdgHCO2198`, approximately 313 bp
- 18SV4: `TAReukFWD1` - `TAReukREV3`, approximately 380 bp
- 18SV9: `1389F` - `1510R`, approximately 149 bp

Please refer to the associated manuscript for primer sequences, PCR conditions, and bioinformatic processing details.

File description

File type	Description
`.fastq.gz`	Compressed demultiplexed raw sequencing reads
`*_R1.fastq.gz`	Forward reads
`*_R2.fastq.gz`	Reverse reads

Data processing note

The files provided here are raw demultiplexed reads and have not been quality-filtered, denoised, clustered, or taxonomically assigned. Downstream processing steps are described in the associated manuscript.

Citation

If you use this dataset, please cite the associated publication once available.

Contact

For questions regarding the dataset, please contact:

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